

Increasing Repeatability of the Perching on Branch for Flapping-Wing Flying Robot

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Abstract—The flapping-wing technology in aerial robotics proposes an alternative way of thrust and lift production rather than the use of high-speed rotary propellers. Those benefits come with the cost of a challenge in take-off and landing. Perching is a good way of landing, similar to real birds in nature; however, impact and slow flight close to perching are difficult tasks. The current flight control presents an average speed of 4(m/s) in the launching and flight, and a slight reduction to 2(m/s) close to perching, approximately. The recently published paper on the perching of flapping-wing flying robots on a branch, on the scale of big-bird size 1.5(m) wingspan, showed a repeatability of 66% [1]. The use of a laser line sensor for last-meter detection and direct actuation of the leg was used to follow the branch close to impact. Here in this work, several modifications have been done to increase the success rate: using feedback on the center-of-mass (CoM) of the robot bird, and the addition of a transformation between the CoM and end-effector of the claw. By this means the correction of the leg-claw position receives feedback from the motion capture system. So, by using more precise feedback and a control transformation, better reliability is expected. The white background for the line sensor is not necessary anymore which is another advantage of this proposed approach. The proposed method resulted in a more reliable way of flight, branch detection, and perching, increasing the repeatability percentage rate to 88.3%.

Keywords: Flapping-wing flying robot, Aerial robotics, Perching, FWFR, UAVs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The perching on a branch using an ornithopter, similar to real birds, has been a challenge in flapping-wing robotics [1]. The perching using leg and claw was addressed [2], [3]; however, using the flapping-wing flying system, a continuous oscillation will be imposed on the system [4]. Roderick et al. proposed a bird-inspired dual-leg system with a similar claw to them [2]. The system was installed under a quadrotor for performing the flight and four phases of aerial, absorption,

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Fig. 1. The perching of a robotic bird on a branch. This image was taken in the live demonstration with the coverage of many news agencies, on the “Energy-Efficient Flapping-Wing Robots Workshop” on September 22, 2023 in Seville, Spain, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-t7p-Lgtm2g>.

anchoring, and adjustment. A perching mechanism for a lightweight flapping-wing system was presented with the possibility of attaching to and detaching from trees, walls, etc. [5]. Thomas et al. adapted a single leg-claw mechanism for perching on a tube or a branch based on the motion of a bald eagle [6]. The carrier of the perching system was a multi-rotor aerial vehicle using geometric control. Perching using multi-rotor systems is still a hot topic in the research community to show the advantages of rapid landing [7]–[11].

The application of laser line sensors was reported in robotics such as weld bead recognition [12], robotic laser welding [13], hand-eye calibration [14], etc. A laser line sensor was used in the detection phase of the perching as well [1], [15]. The very lightweight sensor along with a “seeduino” processor was placed on the leg-claw system of the flapping-wing robot to detect the branch on the last meter approaching area. The line sensor needed a good contrast between the branch and the background which was solved by the installation of a white sheet behind the branch. In this work, the data of the laser line sensor is replaced with the feedback of the OptiTrack system on the center-of-mass (CoM) of the robot. Next, a transformation and controller are designed to regulate the leg towards the branch position while flying close to impact. The precision of the system and the success rate of the operation are a function of the oscillation of the robot bird.

Fig. 2. The schematic of the launching to perching scenario with proposed method; definition of the leg and servomotor angles.

This oscillation adds a disturbance of $[10 - 15](\text{cm})$ in z -axis direction [4]. An equivalent dynamic system modeling was presented to estimate the effect of the disturbance on the CoM of the robot [16], [17]. Previously, the success rate of the perching by the flapping-wing robot was reported at 66% [1]. Here an increase in the success rate from 66% to 88.3% is reported. A geometric transformation is used to design the input law of the leg based on the position of the branch and center of mass of the robot bird. The schematic of the detection and actuation of the leg are shown in Fig. 2.

The flight controller is a combination of linear controllers on flapping, and tail controllers. The flapping frequency controls the height of the robot, provided that an approximate pitch angle is maintained during the flight [1]. The control of the flapping wing systems also used a linear proportional-derivative (PD) along with a trajectory generator based on minimal longitudinal dynamics [18]. Despite the implementation of linear controllers on flapping-wing robots [19]–[21], this type of robotic system was not limited to them and demonstrated maneuvers through adaptive controller [22]–[24], linear quadratic regulator [25], [26] and nonlinear optimal controller SDRE [4]. Moving toward bio-inspired claw presents advantages such as lightweight actuators (shape memory alloys). Using the SMA provided the possibility of adding two legs for holding the branch [27]. Maintaining the pitch angle of the robot using the elevator in the tail using a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) resulted in height control, and regulation to a fixed desired point. The bird starts the flight from a launching mechanism that generates $4(\text{m/s})$ initial speed. The flight zone is close to $15(\text{m})$ closed space inside the OptiTrack zone. The robot must be regulated to the branch in this limited space.

Contribution: Increasing the repeatability of the perching mechanism in the FWFR to 88.3% using a control design and transformation based on the feedback of the system, mechanical modification of the claw, and increasing the leg power. This increment novelty is compared with the previous implementation of a line sensor on the leg which reported 66% success rate [1].

Section II expresses the proposed design and transforma-

tion to increase the perching success. Section III presents a simple simulator to check the validity of the transformation. Section IV is devoted to results and experimental analysis. Conclusions are stated in Section V.

II. PROPOSED DESIGN

Linear PID controllers regulate flapping frequency which is responsible for height control in z -axis, rudder in the tail which is responsible for yaw ψ control, and elevator for pitch angle θ . The robot flies from the launcher to the branch. During the flight, the OptiTrack system reports the CoM of the robot bird to the main processor of the FWFR, a NanoPi NEO board. The actuator of the leg is a FrSky Xact HV5403 servomotor with $22(\text{kgf.cm})$ at $7(\text{V})$, with $72(\text{g})$ weight. This actuator receives a controlled command presented in the following transformation.

Considering the CoM of the robot as known reliable feedback by the motion capture system, the angle between the leg and horizon, aiming the branch position, is:

$$\gamma(t) = \arctan \frac{z_{\text{branch}} - z_c(t) + a_4 \sin \theta_t - a_5 \cos \theta_t}{x_{\text{branch}} - x_c(t) - a_4 \cos \theta_t + a_5 (\sin \theta_t - 1)}, \quad (1)$$

where $a_4, a_5(\text{m})$ are the length of links of the leg, Fig. 2, $x_c(t), z_c(t)(\text{m})$ are CoM position of the bird, $x_{\text{branch}}, z_{\text{branch}}(\text{m})$ are position of the branch in the OptiTrack test bed, and $\theta_t(\text{rad})$ is the trim angle of the leg. The trim angle is a desired angle between the z -axis and a_5 link, i.e. in Fig. 2, θ_t is set $\pi/2(\text{rad})$ though it is adjustable.

It must be noted that the leg is one degree of freedom with a fixed L -shape. Then the command to the servomotor of the leg is defined as:

$$\beta(t) = -\theta(t) - \theta_t + \gamma(t), \quad (2)$$

in which $\theta(t)(\text{rad})$ is pitch angle of the robot. The new transformation (1) and (2) are coded into the control loop of the robot and receive the pitch angle and position coordinates from the OptiTrack. This modification increases the precision of the command to the leg.

Depending on the definition of the axis, the direction of the $\theta(t)$ in (2) might be reversed.

III. SIMULATION

The leg-claw parameters and geometry are added to the FWFR model [4]. The model is six-degree-of-freedom (DoF) including the position and orientation of the robot:

$$\mathbf{q}(t) = [x_c(t), y_c(t), z_c(t), \phi(t), \theta(t), \psi(t)]^\top, \quad (3)$$

where $(x_c(t), y_c(t), z_c(t))$ (m) denote the CoM position of the bird and $(\phi(t), \theta(t), \psi(t))$ (rad) present the orientation angles. The state vector of the system is chosen as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}(t) \\ \mathbf{v}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{v}_2(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_1(t)$ and $\mathbf{v}_2(t)$ are linear and angular velocity of the robot bird. Computing the time derivative of state vector (4) results in the state-space representation of the system in the following form:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{1}{m_b} \mathbf{F}_B \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2) \mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2) \boldsymbol{\tau}_B \\ \mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_1 \\ \mathbf{T}(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_2 \\ \mathbf{R}_b^{-1}(\xi_2) \left(\frac{1}{m_b} \mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2) \mathbf{E}_w(z_c, z_w) - m_b g \mathbf{e}_3 - \dot{\mathbf{R}}_b(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_1 \right) \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2) \left(-\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2) \mathbf{c}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2) - \dot{\mathbf{T}}(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_2 \right) \end{bmatrix} + \quad (5)$$

where the details of the matrices and vectors could be found in Ref. [4]. The controller in the translation part is linear and the orientation part is nonlinear optimal control. The algebraic transformation of the proposed method is added to the model to reflect the motion of the leg-claw system. Considering the initial and final condition of the experiment in the perching test, the simulator provides the following results. The position of the center of mass of the system is demonstrated in Fig. 3. The orientation angles are plotted in Fig. 4. The view of the system with its claw and leg mechanism is illustrated in Fig. 5, which shows that the transformation works perfectly in the simulator.

To show the correctness of the transformation, another approach with different desired pitch angle is shown in Fig. 6. The desired pitch angle in Fig. 5 was -0.55 (rad) and in Fig. 5 was 0.2 (rad), both of them controlled the leg successfully towards the branch despite the oscillations in the trajectory due to the flapping of wings.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The objective of this work is to increase the repeatability of the perching or better to say the success rate. The following steps have been taken to achieve this goal:

- Tuning of the controller to reach the height of the branch faster which gives time to the controller to reduce the error.
- Increasing the power grip of the claw by modifying the spikes and increasing the spring load on the claw. This new fixed configuration of spikes avoids rotation of them through the impact.

Fig. 3. The CoM of the FWFR in regulation towards the branch.

Fig. 4. The orientation of the FWFR in regulation towards the branch.

- Removing the line sensor and using the OptiTrack feedback. The quality of the signal of the motion capture system is much higher than that of the laser sensor and since both experiments were performed in the indoor testbed, the switching to better feedback was justified in this work.
- Selecting a stronger servomotor for the leg and using the transformation and new control law for actuating the leg despite the oscillation of the robot in flight. The impact due to the perching transfers to the body of the robot through the leg and the servo joint; hence, using a stronger servomotor as long as the weight is within the limited payload of the system is helpful.

The coding and implementation are done using C programming language in NanoPi NEO onboard electronics. When the command is sent to the robot, it starts the control loop, from launching to flight, control, and perching automatically. The initial height of the robot is 1.8(m) and the final position is the height of the branch. A preliminary phase of tuning is using a soft branch to avoid crashes and damage to the bird if the height control is not yet adjusted. The soft branch is a rope, attached with almost similar height to the real branch with flexibility in motion after the impact and the possibility of locking the claw around it. The proposed data has been gathered in approximately six months for 60 flights on a soft branch on different occasions. The leg could detect and adjust itself if the error between the CoM and the branch is

Fig. 5. The xz -plane view of the flight close to the impact to the branch with $-0.55(\text{rad})$ pitch angle.

Fig. 6. The xz -plane view of the flight close to the impact to the branch with $0.2(\text{rad})$ pitch angle.

less than $15(\text{cm})$. So, for all the data if the error is more than that, the flight was considered a failure, and otherwise a success. The flight trajectories are demonstrated in Fig. 7. Rarely the data was lost for less than a second in some flights which can be seen as some jumps in the trajectories, Fig. 7, even though those flights reached the perching zone without a problem. The corresponding data is presented in Table I.

The best results was gained $6.5600 \times 10^{-4}(\text{m})$, the worst case was obtained 0.9179 , also median and mean $0.0542, 0.0796$, respectively. The standard deviation was defined as 0.1222 . Considering the error in height control more than $15(\text{cm})$ as a failure, the success rate was computed as 88.3% . After gaining enough data and tuning the controller and operation of the leg flawlessly, the soft branch was removed. The real branch was installed on top of an aluminum structure at the corner of the flight zone. The perching on the real branch has been done several times as well.

Four successful perchings have been shown in the video presentation of this paper and the results of the three of them are presented here. The success rate of the previous work was obtained for real branch (all flights) and scored 66% [1]; however, in this work, 60 flights performed with soft branch and recorded (see Table I) to compute the success rate and

Fig. 7. The flight trajectories of the system in tuning phase and soft branch experiments, 60 records.

Fig. 8. The perching trajectories of the system on the real branch.

tune the system. After tuning, all four flights perched on the branch.

The increase in reliability provided three perching results on the real branch, shown in Fig. 8. The snapshots of the perching experiment are shown in Fig. 9. The best, worst, median, mean, and standard deviation were found at $0.0068, 0.0573, 0.0327, 0.0323$ and $0.0253(\text{m})$, respectively. The significant decrease in the standard deviation shows the enhancement in the proposed design. The regulation error in all of them was found to be less than $7(\text{cm})$, and all of them were in the operating domain of the leg.

Finally, the results of perching were demonstrated live with the coverage of many news agencies, on the “Energy-Efficient Flapping-Wing Robots Workshop” on September 22, 2023 in Seville, Spain¹.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented an experimental study on the perching of a flapping wing robot bird in an indoor testbed. The recent advances in the indoor and outdoor flight of the FWFR showed significant improvement in the control of these robots and led the researchers towards applications such as monitoring, manipulation, and perching. Here in this work, the reliability of the perching has been improved by a series of changes and designing a transformation for the leg-claw control. The results of many experiments on the soft branch and real branch were reported and the video demonstration of these flights are presented as supplementary material of this work.

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-t7p-Lgtn2g>

TABLE I
THE FLIGHT DATA AND ERROR IN HEIGHT CONTROL FOR THE FWFR.

No.	$e(t_f)(m)$	No.	$e(t_f)(m)$	No.	$e(t_f)(m)$	No.	$e(t_f)(m)$
1	0.0597	16	0.0301	31	0.0146	46	0.0300
2	0.1581	17	0.0246	32	0.0447	47	0.0403
3	0.1514	18	0.0118	33	0.0880	48	0.1073
4	0.1380	19	0.0820	34	0.0238	49	0.0685
5	0.0958	20	0.9179	35	0.0088	50	0.0762
6	0.0446	21	0.0091	36	0.0007	51	0.0068
7	0.0133	22	0.0183	37	0.0124	52	0.0554
8	0.0107	23	0.0165	38	0.0180	53	0.0241
9	0.0684	24	0.0624	39	0.0824	54	0.0990
10	0.0352	25	0.0590	40	0.1365	55	0.0067
11	0.1568	26	0.1174	41	0.0315	56	0.0369
12	0.1697	27	0.0766	42	0.1171	57	0.0775
13	0.1427	28	0.0056	43	0.2062	58	0.0142
14	0.2013	29	0.0162	44	0.0522	59	0.1307
15	0.0460	30	0.1072	45	0.0663	60	0.0529

Fig. 9. The snapshots of the experiment of flight and perching on the branch, showing the whole process of launching to perching. (a) shows the launching point at the beginning. (b) and (c) present the flight at 2 and 3 (s). (d) demonstrates the beginning of the detection zone. (e) shows the regulation of the leg before impact. (f) finally shows the robot perched on the branch. The videos of all the experiments, soft and real branches, are shown in the supplementary video of this work, available on the YouTube channel of the GRVC as well.

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